

Saving a Marine Iron Paddle Wheel Removed from the 1868 Steam Engine Shipwreck 'Patris' during an Economic Crisis in Greece

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In October 2006, the famous 1868 steam engine shipwreck "Patris" was visited off the coast of the Greek island Kea, and one of its two iron paddle wheels was removed and taken for exhibition outdoors at the Ermoupolis Industrial Museum in Syros. The paddle wheel removed weighs around 8 tons with an outer wheel diameter of 6.8 m, and a paddle iron shaft measuring 5 m in length. The planned conservation for the wheel after its removal from the sea did not take place due to the looming economic crisis in Greece, and it remained on the port of Syros until 2008 when a sponsor was found to help fund this salvage conservation project. However, many conservation professionals did not wish to undertake the project due to the difficulties and cost involved in stabilizing the marine iron using traditional conservation methods. The TEI of Athens in collaboration with the NTUA applied a novel and cost-effective method to dechlorinate the wheel using impressed current in-situ. The method of the applying impressed current is commonly applied by industry to remove chlorides from reinforced concrete with steel bars. However, to our knowledge it has never been applied to conserve large cultural heritage metal objects.

The paper describes the difficult operation of moving the wheel for outdoor exhibition to the museum from the port, its process of dechlorination, and the cleaning and protection carried out and completed by March 2013. The diagnosis of condition of the wheel is also discussed, such as, in-situ X-Ray Radiography, which was applied to decide if the wheel could be moved without causing collapse of the structure. Our research into this method of applying impressed current to stabilize the iron found that it is possible to remove the majority of chlorides without causing hydrogen embrittlement of the remaining metal. The method of dechlorination of the wheel are given along with the details of the conservation work of this large marine object with limited funds. As well, our current research will attempt to apply this method to dechlorinate the metal part of marine composite artifacts without complete immersion of such objects in an electrolytic solution.

1. Introduction

There was a lot of excitement surrounding the lifting, and removal of the 8 ton iron paddle wheel from the 1868 Shipwreck "Patris" found in 2006 near Kea island, Greece, which is considered important because ships of this kind that used paddle wheels were made just

before the use of a propeller system, and most of ships from this period were wooden. The ship 'Patris' was owned by the Hellenic Steamship Company, the first sea service founded in Greece based in Syros. It was built in 1860 in England by C. Lungley & Co., Deptford on the order by the then Greek King Otto. It was a luxury ship with sails, a 180 horsepower engine, where coal was used to fuel the steam engine, and set in motion its two paddle wheels. On February 23, 1868, the steamer "Patris" with 400 passengers departed from Piraeus to Syros, and sank after hitting a reef near the island of Kea without casualties. The ship was cut in two, and lays today in around 50 m underwater.

One of the two paddles wheels was removed from the sea in 2007 at a depth of 52 meters, and a 40 minute film documentary was created and distributed in 2008 to mark the event (Mentogiannis & Nikolaidis, 2008). Despite assurances that the paddle wheel and other finds removed from the sea and transported to the island of Syros would be properly conserved, with political changes and the looming economic crisis in Greece, planned actions using public funds quickly halted. As a result, the paddle wheel remained on the port of Syros from May 2007, until a team of specialists and a donor could be found to carry out the project. The main author of this paper was approached to treat the wheel in September 2007, after the wheel had already been removed from the sea and the majority of encrustations had been removed with a hammer and chisel. Most conservation professionals at this stage refuse to carry out conservation of such a marine find where it has been allowed to dry out, since the integrity of the object has been compromised (i.e., aesthetic, archaeological or physical). Also, the funds to set up traditional electrolytic methods to stabilize such a large object were nonexistent. Given the significance of the object, refusing to undertake the challenge to conserve the remaining object would mean the complete destruction of the object in time and an embarrassment to the local community of Syros.

The main author approached the School of Chemical Engineering NTUA to try and find an economically viable solution to help dechlorinate the large marine find, since world-wide traditional conservation treatments for large marine iron or composite artifacts are time consuming and very costly or there are still no adequate solutions for treating effectively composite (metal with wood) artifacts without compromising the integrity of the object. Traditionally, electrolysis is carried out by completely immersing large metal objects, such as anchors etc in large electrolytic baths (Lacoudre & Degrigny , 1999) (Elsener & Angst, 2007) . Such methods require suitable facilities, highly trained specialists, and supervision of such treatments over a long duration (in some cases up to two years) (Guilminot & et al., METAL 2007, 2007). The NTUA had extensive experience in the application of impressed current to remove chlorides from iron rebars in porous materials, such as concrete as is commonly applied by industry (Batis, Kouloumbi, & Pantazopoulou, 2005) (Batis & Rakanta, 2005) (Kouloumbi & Batis, 1992). While the degree of corrosion for iron rebars in concrete varies greatly from dried out marine iron, nonetheless, the fact that many of the encrustations were removed, the chlorides found at the metal-corrosion interface are now easily reachable by electrolytic solution given the extensive degree of flaking and cracking at the surface. The paper describes how this conservation project was carried out and completed on a tight economic budget.

Figure 1 The Paddle Steam Engine "Patris"

Figure 2 The Drawing depicts the Shipwreck 'Patris' as it was found off the coast of Kea island where it sank in 1868

Figure 3 The removal of one of the Paddle Wheels from the Shipwreck 'Patris' and its transportation to the island of Syros

Figure 4 The condition of the Paddle Wheel 'Patris' upon its removal from the Sea in May 2007

2. The Economic Situation and Main Difficulties for the Conservation Project

Our main difficulty in undertaking this project is that the total cost raised by the donation was well below the actual cost of the conservation work. Also, the team of engineers and conservators were all based in Athens, four hours away from the island of Syros by Ferryboat. Thus, without additional support by the Municipality of Syros and the Friends of the Museum of Syros the project was not viable. Finally, the conservation of the Wheel could not begin until it was moved to its final location for exhibition some 2 km away from the port. At the port, the wheel was periodically being hit by breaking waves, and any dechlorination attempt at this location would have been counterproductive due to the continuous salt spray conditions.

A donor, the Giorgos M. Pateras family agreed to fund the project, and contracts were made based on their donation between the Municipality of Syros and the Friends of the Museum of Syros with the TEI of Athens for 30.000 Euros in September 2008, and 25.000 in July 2012 respectively for which the conservation project was completed in March 2013. Also,

agreements were made that some supplies, scaffolding, and accommodation costs in Syros for the team would be covered by the Municipality or the Friends of the Museum.

The total budget of 55.000 Euros was for carrying out the condition reports of the object at various stages, which included documentation, scientific analyses, in-situ X-Ray Radiographic analysis as well as dechlorination using impressed current for the entire wheel at two different stages by professional engineers, and finally cleaning and coating by professional conservators. The main delay in completing the conservation project was the difficult operation to move the wheel from the port of Syros to its final location of exhibition outside the Industrial Museum of Syros, an operation that was the responsibility of the Museum. Thus, before moving the wheel, a suitable base had to be designed by a civil engineer to support the weight of the wheel, as well as constructed for its display outside the museum. Also, a condition report of the wheel was necessary to determine if the structure was stable enough to withstand lifting and transporting it without further destruction to the object after over 3 years of removal from the sea. Given the financial difficulties and changing Directorship of the Museum, it was not until September 2010 that the wheel was successfully transported and placed on its base by around 10 skilled workers from the shipping company, NEORION, who volunteered their services and freely offered the use of their crane and vehicle for transport, under the supervision of a civil engineer who designed the base. The wheel had to be lifted and rotated at 90° to be placed on its shaft to the supporting concrete base. The transport had to be carried out in the early hours of the morning since electricity lines from electrical poles had to be lifted at various points during the transport.

Figure 5 The transportation and placement of the Paddle Wheel 'Patris' on its concrete base outside the Industrial Museum of Syros in September 2010

3. The Construction and Condition of the Paddle Wheel after its Removal from the Sea

The Paddle Wheel of the Shipwreck 'Patris' is a 'feathered' sidewheel, which looks like a 'ferris' wheel with an iron frame. The iron frame of the wheel has 11 radial arms on the each side of the axel respectively. These radial arms are attached to the inner and outer rim on each side of the wheel, changing angles. The radial inner arm is 1.4m and with a total length to the outer rim of 2.6 m. The inner and outer rim circumference of the wheel is 4.4 m and 6.8 m respectively. There is a distance of 1.4m separating the interior and exterior part of the wheel. There are 22 paddle blades or 'floats' made of wood paired on 11 radial axes on each side of the wheel, each having their own short arms angled at about 120° connected to another longer radial arm or rod with pins or pivots and with a horizontal iron bar connecting to each pair of floats between on the pivots. The radial arms or rods are connected to a gear (lid with a centre and is capable of revolving) and it controlled the swivel angle of each float. Four meters from end of the paddle shaft is a cone shaped cap, which was used as a trap. The oil trap gathered the oil used to move crankshaft, and this trap measures 2.9m diameter and 2.6m radius and 1 m height made from three sections of metal pieces welded together and held in place with rivets. The exterior part of the cap has a metal brace to hold it in place to the shaft and the axel of the wheel with nuts and bolts.

There is another important reference that describes a similar sunken side-wheeler steamer (S.S. Pevensey) constructed by the same company Charles Lungley of Deptford (<http://www.computer-therapy.com/sidco/files/pevensey.pdf>), the article provides reference to a

scientific explanation on the way such paddle wheels operated at that time (Lardner, 1840).

Figure 6 A schematic drawing of 'feathered' side wheels taken from Lardner (1840)

Figure 7 The photo shows the axel of the 'Patris' Paddle wheel connecting the 11 radial arms on both sides of the axel to the inner and outer part of the wheel. The gear connecting the long radial arms leading to the floats are also shown, which controls the swivel angle of each float. (Photo taken after conservation)

Figure 8 The photo shows outer radial arms attached to the inner and outer rim of one side of the wheel. Also the horizontal iron rods connecting each pair of floats are also shown, and these rods are connected short back arms using pivots (not shown here), which are then connected to the longer radial arms shown in Figure 6. (Photo taken after conservation)

Figure 9 The photo shows the axel of the wheel connected to the paddle shaft, and metal brace used to join the half -moon shaped trap to the shaft which is held in place with nuts and bolts.(Photo taken before conservation at the port of Syros in April 2010)

The paddle wheel is made of puddle wrought iron (WI), which was commonly used for forging large anchors and shafts for steam engine ships by 1860 in Britain (McQueen, 2010). For puddled WI the microstructure of the slag stringers are irregular resulting from primary hammering process (McQueen, 2010). Figure 10 shows the ferrite structure with the irregularly shaped slag inclusions from a sample taken from the 'Patris' paddle wheel. Chemical analysis by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy of the WI of the wheel verifies that it contains no carbon, and the presence of trace amounts of Mn wt. % (0.139), S (0.023), P (0.141), and Si (0.141) are from the slag fibres present in the wrought iron. The construction of the paddle wheel required the use of WI nuts and bolts as well as rivets to join together its iron pieces. The wheel's paddle blades, known as floats were made of wood, and it is mentioned that elm was commonly used at that time (Fletcher, 1910).

Figure 10 Shows the microstructure of the paddle wheel, the ferrite structure with the irregularly shaped slag inclusions, suggesting puddled WI (x200 magnification).

When the paddle wheel was lifted from the Aegean Sea in May 2007, it was encrusted with layers of calcium carbonate, magnesium hydroxide, and iron corrosion products as well as shells and barnacles.

Figure 11 Shows the Encrustations found on the 'Patris' Wheel prior to its conservation in 2008.

When the iron paddle wheel was removed from the sea and exposed to the air, the ferrous compounds found at the metal-corrosion interface oxidized to a ferric state. These rapid changes resulted in physical and chemical damage to the object as shown in Equations 1 or 2, since the iron corrosion product formed (β -FeOOH, akaganeite) is 3 times more voluminous and HCl continues to corrode the remaining metal. This process known as 'active' corrosion, and continues to form soluble ferrous chlorides, and dissolve the remaining iron metal (equations 3 and 4). The process will not stop until all the chlorides ions are removed from the object due to the phenomena known as 'acid regeneration cycle' (Selwyn, Sirois, & Argyropoulos, 1999).

Or

The object upon drying without dechlorination treatment undergoes spalling, cracking, and flaking and continues to disintegrate until it eventually turns to dust. Since the 'Patris' paddle wheel had an extensive bulk metal remaining, this process can take longer than smaller iron

objects removed from the sea. However, the damage done during the abrupt drying out at the port of Syros without stabilization treatment is enormous, since important information is contained within the thick corrosion layers of the object. For this reason, conservation must include a preservation of those layers, and the resulting spalling and flaking of the corroded surface makes it impossible to retain this information. Unfortunately, still today there many who try to treat archaeological terrestrial or marine iron containing metal using only mechanical cleaning, thinking that if they remove the corrosion layers they can remove the chlorides. Not only is this impossible, since the chlorides are retained right next to the metal below the corrosion layers, but removing those corrosion layers loses the integrity of the object. Many have also argued that once archaeological iron has been left to dry out and the soluble FeCl_2 has changed to akaganeite, it is much easier to dechlorinate using electrolytic methods even though the integrity of the object has been compromised (Guilminot, et al., 2012)

Figure 12 The Photo depicts the 'active' corrosion for the 'Patris' wheel as signs of spalling, flaking, and akaganeite formation at the metal/corrosion interface. The piece held to the right is the encrustation layer with a corrosion layer showing signs of akaganeite, with the bottom piece being the metal part of the inner frame of the wheel also showing akaganeite formation.

In March 2009, a portable X-Ray Radiography system, was transported to Syros and around 15 X-rays were taken at various points of the iron frame of the paddle wheel to determine the amount of remaining metal and the condition. The unit is a second-hand Military control Unit and Tube Transformer Head, X-Ray Apparatus 15 m.A., Mobile-Portable, Stock No. - 6-013-680, manufactured

by Picker X-Ray Corp., Waite MFG. DIV., Cleveland, Ohio, U.S.A., and the films were processed at the local hospital in Syros.

Figure 13 The set-up of Radiographic film during the in-situ X-ray Radiography of various parts of the 'Patris' Wheel

Figure 14 The Radiographic Image for the position shown in Figure 10, where the light white area indicates iron metal remaining

Although, it was obvious that the rapid changes that resulted from removal of the paddle wheel from the sea to the port of Syros caused extensive spalling, cracking and formation of 'active' corrosion and loss of the original surface of the object. There was extensive metal core remaining to allow for stabilization treatment so as to preserve the remaining shape of the 'paddle' wheel. The condition survey also concluded that the paddle wheel was safe to lift and transport to its final exhibition location without collapse of the structure.

4. The Dechlorination of the Paddle Wheel using Impressed Current

The dechlorination process of the entire iron frame of the 'Patris' paddle wheel using impressed current took place in at two different stages: first from December 2010 to the end of February 2011 after the wheel was moved from the port to its final location; second, from October 2012 to February 2013 during final cleaning and prior to coating of the wheel. The procedure was as follows:

- a) Each selected area of the wheel was first rinsed locally using deionized water. At least three rinses were needed to remove dust and any other soluble salts on the surface of the wheel.
- b) A sponge with composition, 60% natural sponge, 40% polyurethane, thickness of 4cm was used to encase each section of the wheel soaked (for around 2 hours) in 0,1 M NaOH solution in deionized water. The sponge material was held in place around the wheel using iron wire.
- c) On top of the sponge the stainless steel type 316 with 2mm thickness was placed, which acted as an anode. The anode (positive pole) was fastened in contact to the sponge using insulated copper wires, ensuring that the anode did not come in contact with the wheel acting as a cathode.
- d) The wheel is connected to the negative pole (by drilling a small hole near the shaft of the wheel), and adding a screw and bolt to hold the connection.
- e) The positive and negative poles with cables and crocodile clips were connected to the transformer/rectifier (24V, 10A) and direct current was applied for 24 hours to each section of the wheel at $15\text{mA}/\text{m}^2$ current density.
- f) During the 24 hour process more electrolytic solution was poured onto the sponge to ensure that it remained wet during the 24 hours of applying current using 1,5 L bottles containing 0.1 M NaOH solution with a drip channel (holes in the bottle) connected to the sponge.
- g) After the 24 hours, the stainless steel anode and sponge was removed, and the treated wheel was completely rinsed with deionized iron to remove any residual NaOH solution from the surface of the metal.
- h) After the application of impressed current, samples were collected from the sponge to determine the amount of chlorides removed.
- i) This process was repeated until each metal section of the wheel was treated using this method.

Figure 15 A photo showing how the impressed current was applied to the shaft of the 'Patris' wheel

The methodology outlined above was tested in the laboratory on a piece of the 'Patris' paddle wheel in order to determine best current density and duration needed to remove the most amount of chlorides in the selected sponge. Also, chloride analysis was carried out during the testing procedure in the lab as well as in-situ in Syros to determine the amount of chlorides removed, and if additional applications to the wheel would be beneficial. The testing procedure is to be published in a forthcoming scientific paper. In summary, our results found that at least 24 hours is required to reach an equilibrium in the removal of the most amount of chlorides from the surface of the metal into the type of sponge we used. Also, two applications for the dechlorination process using impressed current removed somewhere between 75-90% of the total chlorides on the surface of the metal. Our results agree well with (Guilminot, et al., 2012) where the fastest kinetics for chloride removal when comparing different types of marine iron (dry and wet) was for those stored in air for two years where 85% of the chlorides were extracted in 10% of the treatment time using electrolysis with complete immersion of the objects. However, the study showed that overall less chlorides were removed from dried out marine iron when compared to wet

marine iron, since the dried out material has lost a large degree of its corrosion products containing chlorides.

We are now at the stage where we are repeating our experiments using this technique under Research Funding Program, **ARCHIMEDES III** to determine the total amount of chlorides remaining in the metal after the application of this method (by completely dissolving our marine iron samples). Also, we will carry out scientific analysis of the types of corrosion products before and after the impressed current application to verify if the akaganeite is being transformed to magnetite. Eventually, our goal is to scale down the method to be able to apply such a technique for dechlorination of marine composite artifacts (metal with wood or textile) to the metal part of the object without damaging the organic part. To date only near-neutral electrolytes have been used to dechlorinate marine composite artifacts using complete immersion electrolysis (de Groot & Degriigny, 2004), and to the best of our knowledge there has been no research into the application of impressed current selectively applied to metal parts of composite objects as an alternative method to stabilize the metal.

5. Cleaning, Consolidation, and Coating of the 'Patris' Wheel

During the second stage of the dechlorination procedure professional conservators worked together with the professional engineers to clean certain parts of the wheel that had some encrustations remaining to ensure the application of impressed current to each section would be the most effective at reaching the surface containing chlorides. After the dechlorination procedure, an epoxy resin (Araldite 2 part epoxy adhesive) had to be used in certain locations where there was extensive exfoliation of the metal, in order to consolidate these parts, and ensure the best coating application.

Figure 16 Araldite 2 part epoxy adhesive was used to consolidate exfoliated areas of the metal frame as well as cracks prior to coating

A coating had to be selected that could withstand the outdoor conditions of salt aerosol environment in Syros, and until a roof can be built for the 'Patris' Paddle wheel it will come in direct contact with the rain during the winter season. Furthermore, the selected coating needed to last for at least 5 years. The main author of the paper contacted Stefan Brüggerhoff of the German Mining Museum to advise on a possible coating for the wheel, and he put us in contact with the company, Dr. A. Conrads Lacke GmbH & Co. KG to try one of two types of coatings: a corrosion protection wax emulsion, XR-000053 or a two part coating system Primer PD-000090-UV and Top coat glossy layer PD-000073-UV. These coatings were applied on the wheel in the Fall of 2010 according to the manufacturer's specifications to selected test areas. After one year, it was found that the tested area coated with the wax emulsion had signs of pinpoint rusting, whereas there was no signs of coating failure with the two part coating system. However, the appearance of the two part coating system was very shiny as opposed to the wax emulsion which had a more matt appearance. It was therefore decided to apply first the two part coating system followed by a final application of the wax emulsion. The professional conservator tested the coatings in the laboratory on a test piece taken from the 'Patris' wheel as well as plexiglass using a brush, and measuring the coating thickness after each application in order to become familiar with the handling of the coating and to determine the amount required to reach the minimum amount of the thickness recommended by the manufacturer. The specifications of each coating allows for application during the mild winter months in Greece, as long as it is not above RH 80-90% and minimum temperatures of between 5-10°C.

The coatings were applied to the 'Patris' Wheel in February and March 2013 where the temperatures were as low as 10°C (during the evenings) and as high as 20° C (during the day), and with average RH of around 70%. The application during the winter months had the disadvantage that it would take at least one day to a day and half for a layer of coating to dry completely. So the coating process would take longer, since additional layers could not be applied until the previous one was completely dry. The conservators found it very satisfactory in applying the primer of the two part coating system, which could easily spread to the uneven and rough surface of the 'Patris' wheel. It should be noted that the wax emulsion coating can only be removed with high pressure hot water blasting, and the two part coating system by mechanical means, since solvents cannot dissolve the coating. We believe that the use of this type of coating system is justified given the outdoor conditions for the exhibition of the wheel, and subsequent difficulties in maintaining the coating surface on the island of Syros as well as the cost involved. Finally, the manufacturer for the 2 part coating system has found from experience that on corroded steel, the corrosion protection of this material will fail after 5-10 years, but strongly recommended that a roof be built over the wheel to maintain the protected surface of the metal.

Figure 17 The application of the coating system of the 'Patris' Wheel in March 1013

Figure 18 An up-close photo of the surface of the 'Patris' Wheel to which the coating was applied in March 2013

Conclusions:

Most finds from shipwrecks are very large objects such as anchors and a large number of the objects found in them are composite, made of metal – leather/fabric/cardboard/wood. World-wide traditional conservation treatments for such artifacts are time consuming and very costly or there are still no adequate solutions for treating effectively composite artifacts without compromising the integrity of the object. Traditionally, electrolysis is carried out by completely immersing large metal objects, such as anchors etc in large electrolytic baths. Such methods require suitable facilities and highly trained specialists. Our work has used another method to dechlorinate such large objects using impressed current as is commonly used by industry. In our opinion, this was the most economical method to ensure the most removal of chlorides from the surface for this dried out marine artifact before coating the object for further protection. It remains for this method to be adapted on wet marine iron that is heavily encrusted as is common in the warm Aegean Sea in Greece. Adapting the technique to wet marine metal or composite artifacts after their removal from the Sea will require considering how to maintain them in a wet state (e.g. using water) to prevent the material loss of the object especially in countries like Greece that have very hot and arid summers.

Many have argued that the 'Patris' wheel should not have been removed from the sea without the funds to carry out its conservation according to international conservation practices as outlined in the UNESCO 2001 Convention on the Protection of the Underwater Cultural Heritage. As authors, we hesitated greatly to undertake this conservation project due to the difficult circumstances behind carrying out its conservation treatment after its removal from the Sea, and due to the fact that the integrity of the object had been compromised prior to our

involvement. Our decision to carry out this project was for the challenge to try to adapt a well-known industrial technique of applying impressed current for stabilizing iron rebars in concrete to the conservation of cultural heritage metals, and to save what is remaining for this important find. We hope that this paper will serve to educate those who may consider in the future to remove such large objects, that the best way to preserve them long-term is in-situ, underwater, using cathodic protection. Conservation of dried out marine metal objects comes with great losses to the archaeological information preserved within those corroded layers, and artifacts should not be removed from the Sea without a prior and effective conservation plan.

Figure 19 A photo of the 'Patris' Wheel after the completion of its conservation and coating in March 2013

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